

BMF CP109: Nigerian Female Business Owners' Financial Access and Solar Energy Adoption

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“Through the trials of life, Kingfisher gains a deep understanding of the world. Naturally, living in this world means understanding the ways of business.”

–In “Bird Village Economics,” [Wild Wise Weird](#) (2024)

1. Project description

1.1. Main objectives

The current study is conducted to examine the following research questions:

- How is access to formal finance associated with the business's adoption of solar energy as the primary or secondary energy source?
- Is the relationship between access to formal finance and the business's adoption of solar energy as the primary or secondary energy source conditional on the business owner being female?
- How is access to informal finance associated with the business's adoption of solar energy as the primary or secondary energy source?
- Is the relationship between access to informal finance and the business's adoption of solar energy as the primary or secondary energy source conditional on the business owner being female?

- How is access to friends/family/relatives' loans associated with the business's adoption of solar energy as the primary or secondary energy source?
- Is the relationship between access to friends/family/relatives' loans and the business's adoption of solar energy as the primary or secondary energy source conditional on the business owner being female?

Findings from this study are expected to contribute to promoting the eco-surplus culture and sustainable development [1].

1.2. Materials

The Granular Interaction Thinking Theory (GITT) will be employed for the conceptual development of this study, while the Bayesian Mindsponge Framework (BMF) analytics will be utilized for statistical analysis [2,3]. The dataset comprises responses from 1122 small and medium-sized enterprises in Nigeria [4]. Statistical analyses will be conducted using the bayesvl R package, which utilizes the Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) algorithm for estimation [5].

For the sake of research transparency and reducing research and reproducibility costs, we have stored all data and computer code on Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/16402672>.

1.3. Main findings

The preliminary analysis suggests that access to formal finance is negatively associated with the adoption of solar energy, and being a female business owner further amplifies the negative effect (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: The estimated posterior distributions.

2. Collaboration procedure

Portal users should follow these steps to register to participate in this research project:

1. Create an account on the website (preferably using an institutional email).
2. Comment your name, affiliation, and your desired role in the project below this post.
3. Patiently wait for the formal agreement on the project from the AISDL mentor.

If you have further inquiries, please contact us at aisdl_team@mindsponge.info

If you have been invited to join the project by an AISDL member, you are still encouraged to follow the above formal steps.

All the resources for conducting and writing the research manuscript will be distributed upon project participation.

AISDL mentor for this project: **Minh-Hoang Nguyen**.

AISDL members who have joined this project: **Quan-Hoang Vuong, Viet-Phuong La**.

The research project strictly adheres to scientific integrity standards, including authorship rights and obligations, without incurring an economic burden at participants' expenses.

References

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[2] Vuong QH, Nguyen MH. (2024). *Better economics for the Earth: A lesson from quantum and information theories*. <https://books.google.com/books?id=I50TEQAAQBAJ>

[3] Vuong QH, Nguyen MH, La VP. (2022). *The mindsponge and BMF analytics for innovative thinking in social sciences and humanities*. Walter de Gruyter GmbH. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/8367405102/>

[4] Pelz S, et al. (2023). Electricity supply quality and use among rural and peri-urban households and small firms in Nigeria. *Scientific Data*, **10**, 273. <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41597-023-02185-0>

[5] Vuong QH, La VP. (2025). Package 'bayesvl' version 1.0.0. <https://books.google.com/books/about?id=znleEQAAQBAJ>

[6] Vuong QH. (2024). *Wild Wise Weird*. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/BOBG2NNHY6>

